

STUDY OF ADJUSTMENT IN RELATION TO SOCIAL SUPPORT AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract

The present study explores adjustment of secondary school students in relation to social support. This study falls under descriptive research design. A sample of 200 students has been taken from six government schools of district Gurdaspur. The participants in this study include 200 secondary school students were selected by random sampling. T-test, SD and two-way ANOVA were applied to the analysis of data and the results found that not significant interaction effect of Adjustment on social support of secondary school students. It found that Adjustment has not impact on social support because of teacher has not interaction with students, lack of usage of instructional variety during teaching. Teacher not came with proper planning in classroom. So in order to raise the level of Adjustment and social support, it is recommended that students should take actively participate and co-curricular activities organized by school.

Keywords: social support, adjustment, secondary school students.

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Introduction

It is the age of globalization where everybody is in race for success. This race begun with the emergence of a humans in this beautiful world .However, ancient time shows that people were only interested in their food. But as people progressed in their lives, the style of living

has also changed rapidly .Gradually science made inventions that motivated people to achieve more in their lives. Due to overall development, people became victim of many problems, as well, whether they related to personal aspirations or desire .When people makes themselves ready to face challenges, it begins with adjustment in their lives. These adjustment require a lot of learning, experience and maturity .The biggest challenge faced is schooling oneself according to one's circumstances, which can be achieved through various means of support in adjusting students. Students deal with a variety of adjustment issues throughout their academic careers, some of which may have an adverse effect on their wellbeing. One third of every 100 kids and teenagers will suffer anxiety of some kind half of these students will have a comorbid mental or behavioural problem, like depression, in addition to their primary mental or behavioural disorder(according to the U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, 2003). Given these concerns, researching factors such as social support that may buffer adolescents from these poor outcomes is critical to determine potential interventions for these students. Significant correlations between perceived social support and student adjustment have been found in the literature, mostly in cross-sectional studies linking social support to other dimensions (Demaray & Malecki, 2002a;Wenz-Gross & Siperstein, 1998; Piko, 2000; Malecki & Demaray, 2003). There haven't been many studies looking at how stable these constructs' relationships to social support are throughout time. The majority cross-sectional research that is currently available has not yet been able to reach the conclusion that social support accurately predicts significant consequences (DuBois et al., 2002). The contributions of social support to adjustment outcomes over time can only be understood by adopting a longitudinal strategy, which is the only way in which the potential long-term correlations between these variables can be effectively studied (DuBois et al., 2002; Malecki & Demaray, 2003). There is a sizable body of research demonstrating the link between social support and adolescent adjustment, as well as between adjustment and behavioural issues (Dunn, Putallaz, Sheppard, & Withdrawn behaviour and hopelessness (Kashani et al., 1994), emotional problems (Garnefski & Diekstra, 1996), depression (Cheng, 1997; Licitra- Kleckler & Waas, 1993), delinquency (Licitra- Kleckler & Waas, 1993), and four lower self-concepts (Forman, 1988; Wenz-Gross).Low levels of peer and family support have been linked to Siperstein, Untch, and Widaman (1997). Warm, encouraging parental behaviours were found to be positively connected to prosocial behaviour and adversely

related to various forms of aggressiveness by Domitrovich and Bierman (2001). Additionally, WenzGross et al. (1997) and Dunn et al. (1987) discovered family support to be connected to academic self-concept and school adjustment. Although to a lesser extent, the relationship between academic assistance (i.e., teacher and school support) and school-related outcomes has been studied. Bursuck and Asher (1986) discovered that if students were poor achievers and had a low sociometric status, teachers assessed them as less academically competent than their peers. Additionally, there is evidence that certain school maladjustment variables, such as attitudes towards education and teachers, sensation seeking, and indicators of academic competence, are associated with teacher support (Demaray & Malecki, 2002b; Malecki). Support for schools 4 has also been discovered to connect with characteristics associated with school maladjustment (Demaray & Malecki, 2002b). 1 An analysis of the data from a previous study, which was crucial to the current investigation, was at one point, there was a correlation between social support and adjustment (Demaray & Malecki, 2002b). 5 Specifically, Demaray and Malecki (2002b) found that the levels of parent and classmate support were related to factors such as depression, stress, and other adjustment factors. 1 Additionally, support from those sources, along with support from close friends, was related to self-esteem and self-concept. Moreover, the level of parent, teacher, and school support was significantly related to students' general attitude towards school and their teachers. In addition to being related to the indicators described above, Demaray and Malecki (2002b) found as expected, teacher and school support related to various aspects of school maladjustment, and school support was related to indicators like social stress, relationships with parents and others, self-esteem, and self-reliance. Revealed parental support was associated to various factors, such as social stress, depression, interpersonal connections, self-esteem, and attitudes towards school. As anticipated, several components of school maladjustment were related to teacher and school assistance. Additionally, variables including social stress, connections with parents and others, self-esteem, and self-reliance were linked to school support. Similar to parental support, peer support was influenced by a number of adjustment characteristics, including anxiety, social stress, depression, relationships with others, and self-reliance. Minority populations and social support. Although social support is crucial for all students, it's also critical to comprehend how minority kids uniquely react to the relationship between social support and adjustment.

Minority teenagers are more likely to drop out of school because of environmental variables such as violence, racism, and poverty are all connected (Gillock & Reyes, 1999). Students from minority backgrounds may experience some of these negative consequences less severely with social assistance. A quick overview of this research is necessary given these unique issues and the fact that the majority of the participants in the current study are Hispanic. According to Gillock and Reyes (1999), the majority of Mexican Americans are women. Participants considered the principal, instructors, and counsellors to be just "somewhat" sympathetic during stressful periods. In turn, this stress was linked to less successful academic performance. According to Demaray and Malecki (2002a), White students. In order to further the body of knowledge on social support, this study looked at how social support affects student adjustment over the long term.

Statement of the problem

Study of Adjustment in relation to Social Support among Secondary School Students.

Delimitations of the problem

The present study was delimited to 200 male and female secondary school students of PSEB of Gurdaspur district.

Objectives

1. To find out the level of social support among secondary school students.
2. To find out the level of adjustment among secondary school students.
3. To find out the relationship between adjustment and social support among secondary school students.
4. To study the level adjustment with respect to gender.
5. To study the level of social support with respect to gender.
6. To study the interaction effect of social support and gender on adjustment of secondary school students.

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant relationship between adjustment and social support of secondary school students.
2. There is no significant difference in adjustment of secondary school students with respect to gender.

3. There is no significant difference in social support of secondary school students with respect to gender.
4. There is no significant interaction effect of social support and gender on adjustment of secondary school students.

Methodology

Descriptive survey method was used in study. Data collection was done from senior secondary school of Gurdaspur district, by technique of simple random sampling. The sample consists 200 senior secondary school students.

Tools

The following tools have been administered on the subjects in study:

Tool 1 Adjustment Scale by V.K.Mittal (1974)

Tool 2 Social Support Scale by Dull and Godara (2016).

Statistical Techniques

To achieve objective of present study investigator will use following descriptive statistical techniques for analysis of the data: mean, standard deviation- ratio, pearson`s correlation coefficient and t-ratio.

Result and Discussion

HYPOTHESIS:1

1. THERE IS NO SIGNIFICANT RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN ADJUSTMENT AND SOCIAL SUPPORT OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

Hypothesis was framed to examine the relationship between adjustment and social support of secondary school students.

To test the hypothesis, correlation was applied to determine the significant difference between adjustment and social support of secondary school students. The result of analysis is being reported in table 4.1

TABLE : 1

		SOCIAL SUPPORT	ADJUSTMENT INVENTORY
SOCIAL SUPPORT	Pearson correlation	1**	0.043**
	Sig.(2 tailed)		.544
	N	200	200
ADJUSTMENT INVENTORY	Pearson correlation	0.043**	1**
	Sig.(2 tailed)	.544	
	N	200	200

Hypothesis 1- There is no significant relationship between adjustment and social support of secondary school students.

It is clear from the table that the correlation was between adjustment and social support is .043** P=.544. The result indicates that adjustment significantly and positively related with adjustment inventory beliefs of secondary school students. Hence, the hypothesis” there will be no significant relationship between adjustment and social support of secondary school students” has been not rejected.

HYPOTHESIS:2

2. THERE IS NO SIGNIFICANT DIFFERENCE IN ADJUSTMENT OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS WITH RESPECT TO GENDER

Hypothesis was framed to examine that there is no significant difference in adjustment of secondary school students with respect to gender.

To test the hypothesis, t test was applied to determine the significant difference adjustment of secondary school students with respect to gender. The result of analysis is being reported in table 2

TABLE : 2

	Gender	N	Mean	SD	Std.Err or Mean	Std.Erro r Differenc e	t - Valu e	p- Valu e
ADJUSTMENT	Male	90	163.8111 1	18.019	1.899	2.2507	1.275	0.204
	Femal e	110	166.6818 2	13.798	1.315	2.3105	1.242	0.216

The table 4.2 reveals that there is significant difference in adjustment of secondary school students with respect to gender. As shown in table 4.2 the mean of secondary school students male is 163.8111 and that female 13.798638 and the SD for two groups was 18.019275 and 13.798638 respectively. It further indicated that the obtained P value of adjustment of gender is greater than the table value 0.05 level. So, our null Hypothesis (2) “there is no significant difference in adjustment of secondary school students with respect to gender “was not rejected. It was concluded the female have higher adjustment score than male students.

HYPOTHESIS: 3

THERE IS NO SIGNIFICANT DIFFERENCE IN SOCIAL SUPPORT OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS WITH RESPECT TO GENDER

Hypothesis was framed to examine that there is no significant difference in social support of secondary school students with respect to gender.

To test the hypothesis, t test was applied to determine the significant difference social support of secondary school students with respect to gender. The result of analysis is being reported in table 4.2

TABLE 4.2

	Gender	N	Mean	SD	Std.Error Mean	Std.Error Difference	t -Value	p-Value
SOCIAL SUPPORT	Male	90	101.3000	8.368	0.882	1.231	1.513	0.132
	Female	110	103.1636	8.897	0.848	1.223	1.523	0.129

The table 4.3 reveals that there is significant difference in social support of secondary school students with respect to gender. As shown in table 4.3 the mean of secondary school students male is 101.3000 and that female 103.1636 and the SD for two groups was 8.36855 and 8.89751 respectively. It further indicated that the obtained P value of adjustment of gender is greater than the table value 0.05 level. So, our null Hypothesis (3) “there is no significant difference in social support of secondary school students with respect to gender “was not rejected. It was concluded the female have higher social support score than male students.

HYPOTHESES 4

THERE IS NO SIGNIFICANT INTERACTION EFFECT OF SOCIAL SUPPORT AND GENDER ON ADJUSTMENT OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS INTERACTION EFFECT ON ADJUSTMENT

DEPENDENT VARIABLES	SOURCE	SUM OF SQUARE	df	MEAN SQUARE	F	SIG.
ADJUSTMENT	GENDER(A)	884.595	1	884.595	3.549	0.061
	Social support(B)	1531.591	6	255.265	1.024	0.411
	GENDER* Social support(A*B)	1815.848	5	249.281	1.457	0.206
ERROR		46615.473	187			

Main effect

- GENDER (A)

It seen from the table that the F-ratio for the difference between the adjustment and gender was 3.549 which in comparison the table value was found to be insignificant at 0.05 level of significance. This suggest that the effect of adjustment on the mean score of gender of two groups was insignificant.

- SOCIAL SUPPORT (B)

It seen from the table that the F-ratio for the difference between the adjustment and social support was 1.024 which in comparison the table value was found to be insignificant at 0.05 level of significance. This suggest that the effect of academic adjustment on the mean score of social support was insignificant.

- INTERACTION BETWEEN SOCIAL SUPPORT AND GENDER (A*B)

It may seen from the table that F-ratio for interaction between gender and social support was 1.457 which is compared to the table value was found to be insignificant at 0.05 level of significance. This suggested that interaction effect on adjustment was insignificant at specified level. Hence, the null hypothesis “There is no significant effect on social support and gender on adjustment of secondary school students” was not rejected. The result indicates that there was insignificant difference in the mean score on adjustment due to interaction effect of gender and score.

Discussion

Results indicate that males do better in terms of adaptability than females in all five areas, with males scoring higher overall. The correlation between social assistance and students' *Copyright © 2023, Scholarly Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies*

adjustment is favourable but negligible. Both men and women have been discovered to share the same traits. Males are generally seen to be better adjusted than girls in terms of their homes, health, social, emotional, and educational lives. The level of adjustment is comparable between men and women. Social support has a small but positive impact on adjustment. Achieving an acceptable balance between one's desire for self realisation and the expectations of the society in which one lives is necessary for social support of adjustment. Making satisfactory connections with the other members of the group is important.

Conclusion

The present study sought to explore the effect of Adjustment and social support. Study revealed that Adjustment no effect on social support. In order to raise the level of Adjustment and Social Support. It is recommended that students should take actively participate in academic and co-curricular activities organized by school.

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